

Two Conservation of Momentum Equations and Quantum Mechanics Part II

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In Part I, we focused on one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon. Here we wish to consider two dimensional reflection-refraction. In particular, we note (as in (1)), that a single photon may either reflect or refract and that one may apply Newton's conservation of momentum to each scenario separately to obtain the equal incident-reflected angle law and Snell's law. The issue is that if one has many photons in a stream, some will reflect and others refract. These two probabilities cannot be calculated using Newtonian mechanics it seems and thus, suggest that a more general theory is needed, namely quantum mechanics.

Momentum conservation must hold as it does in Newtonian mechanics, but we argue that a general theory must somehow include probabilities for reflection and refraction. In other words, we suggest a link between the two requirements instead of each being independent. The reason for this is that in a steady stream situation, one has both the incident momentum, reflected and refracted together and momentum conservation is in space, not time, as in two body scattering. Furthermore, this average steady stream momentum conservation is somehow linked to the probabilities to reflect-refract, i.e. the intensities of the reflected and refracted beams. We suggest that these considerations are associated with a quantum mechanical treatment of the problem which allows for any co-ordinate axis to be used and ultimately leads to Newton's conservation of momentum (one equation), through two equations, one for a kind of probability balance and the other for a momentum balance using this special probability.

Newtonian Mechanics and Two Dimensional Reflection Refraction

Newtonian mechanics, i.e. the conservation of momentum if there is no net force in a direction, holds separately for both a reflected and refracted photon in two dimensions. Physically, this is accurate because a photon either reflects or refracts, it does not do both. Thus, from a Newtonian point of view, one analyses two problems separately.

In the case of reflection:

Reflection: If the n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction) interface lies along the x axis, then there is no force parallel to the x axis and $p(x)_{in} = p(x)_{out}$. If p magnitude is conserved, then the:

angle of incidence = the angle of reflection. ((1))

Refraction: The same requirement for $p(x)_{in} = p(x)_{out}$ exists, but p_{n1} is the incident momentum and p_{n2} the refracted. If $\theta(i)$ is the angle with the y axis of the incoming photon and $\theta(r)$ that of the refracted, also with the y axis, then:

$$p_{n1} \sin(\theta(i)) = p_{n2} \sin(\theta(r)) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is Snell's law. These Newtonian arguments are given in (1).

What is the Issue with the Newtonian Approach?

The Newtonian approach applied separately to reflection and refraction seems to have no problems. The only issue which arises is that there is a probability to reflect and another to refract and this does not seem to be calculable using Newtonian mechanics. In other words, if one created a steady stream picture, then one would have incident, reflected and refracted fluxes as argued in a previous note. If one wishes to have average momentum conservation for this steady stream picture, then the reflected and refracted beams both appear in an equation with the incident beam. Furthermore, momentum conservation in such a picture is in space, not time, because the incident photon and reflected exist in the same space, but at different times. Thus, a quantum mechanical approach is unusual in that it uses Newton's conservation of momentum (on average) together with the removal of time. In the steady stream picture, the average momentum must be calculated using a probability linked to the flux of the particle and so average momentum conservation and the ideas of fluxes or probability are intertwined. This requires negative probability weights in some cases. This also suggests the possibility for two equations, one for probability and the other for average momentum conservation. Nevertheless, these two equations should reproduce the Newtonian conservation of momentum equation $p(x)_{in} = p(x)_{out}$, because this equation is correct. Thus, there are again two different kinds of momentum conservation equations. In this case, one is for a steady stream picture and the other for reflection and refraction separately.

The Question of Invariance in Space

We argue that it is not simply enough to consider probability in terms of a kind of flux in space. There is also a probability linked to x probability along a photon ray. Classically, one would argue that there is equal probability to be at any x point along a ray. If one considers momentum conservation with this probability, then we argue that there are interesting implications on the probability.

Given a momentum vector, one may break it into components $(p(x), p(y))$ using any rotated x - y co-ordinate system. In such a case, one has conservation of momentum or Newton's second law in the x -direction and separately in the y -direction. In other words, one considers each direction separately. This means that one has equal probability to be at any x and equal probability to be at any y . If one considers an axis along the photon motion, then there is also equal probability to be at any point on this ray. Thus:

$$P(\text{point on photon ray}) = P(x) P(y) \quad ((3))$$

((3)) holds for any x, y co-ordinates based on the rotated x - y system. If one were to simply state that $P(x) = \text{constant}$ and $P(y) = \text{constant}$ in ((3)), it seems that this would imply that any x, y pair are acceptable, but this is not the case, because on certain (x, y) pairs map out the photon ray position. We thus suggest that one should have a probability which is invariant under rotations of the x - y co-ordinate system, but allows one to write ((3)), i.e. break out x and y pieces. This suggests the form:

$\exp(i(ax+by))$ where (a,b) is a vector ((4))

We use i to create a periodic function which is associated with constant probability. In fact, equal probability is obtained by multiplying ((4)) by its complex conjugate.

The question now becomes: What is the vector (a,b) ?

It seems that the only relevant vector in the problem is p (momentum). It is the only other vector of a physical quantity which has been considered. We thus suggest using $p=(a,b)$. In this case, one obtains:

$A \exp(ip \cdot r)$ as the probability for motion along a ray. ((5))

If ((5)) is a probability, then one may try to apply its conservation and conservation of average momentum to the 2-dimensional reflection-refraction. We have already stressed that in this case, one considers a steady stream picture so that conservation of momentum is intertwined with probability ((5)). This means mixing events which occur at different times and with different probabilities in the same equation, which differs from the Newtonian approach of treating reflection and refraction separately.

Quantum Mechanical Approach to Snell's Law

We consider an x axis lying along the n_1 - n_2 interface and an incident beam entering making an angle $\theta(i)$ with the y axis. The refracted beam makes an angle $\theta(r)$ with the y axis. Then, one may consider the x motion and y motion independently as in Newtonian mechanics, but this time using $\exp(ipx)$ s and weights A,B,C for the y direction and A_1,B_1,C_1 for the x direction.

It will be seen that one may allow for A,B,C, A_1,B_1,C_1 's to be either positive or negative.

For the y direction:

$$A \exp(-ipn_1 \cos(\theta(i)) y) + B \exp(ipn_1 \cos(\theta(\text{refl}))) = C \exp(ipn_2 \cos(\theta(r))y) \quad ((6))$$

$y=0$ is taken as the interaction point in ((6)) so: $A+B=C$

From a probability point of view, one expects B to be negative because some of A is being removed to allow for C .

The corresponding momentum equation in y is: $-Apn_1 \cos(\theta(i)) - |B|pn_1 \cos(\theta(\text{refl})) = Cpn_2 \cos(\theta(r))$ ((7))

For the x direction:

$$A_1 \exp(ipn_1 \sin(\theta(i))x) = B_1 \exp(ipn_1 \sin(\theta(\text{refl}))x) + C_1 \exp(ipn_2 \sin(\theta(r))x) \text{ or } A_1 = B_1 + C_1 \quad ((8))$$

Here A_1, B_1, C_1 should all be positive, so one finds that $A=A_1, C=C_1$ and $B = -B_1$ where A, C and B_1 are positive is a solution when comparing $A+B=C$ and $A_1=B_1+C_1$.

$$\text{and } A p n_1 \sin(\theta(i)) - |B| p n_1 \sin(\theta(\text{refl})) = C p n_2 \sin(\theta(r)) \quad ((9))$$

It is possible to square ((9)) and ((7)) and add to find:

$$p p + |B| |B| p p - p p |B|^2 (\sin(\theta(i)) - \cos(\theta(i)) \cos(\theta(r))) = C C p_2 p_2 \quad ((10))$$

If one wishes all angular dependence to disappear, one may suggest: $\sin(\theta(i)) = \sin(\theta(\text{refl}))$.

If this is the case, then ((9)) yields Snell's law: $\sin(\theta(i))/\sin(\theta(r)) = n_2/n_1$, where p is really $n_1 p$ and $p_2 = n_2 p$. ((11))

Thus, the quantum steady stream picture involves probabilities which may be negative to allow for reductions in probability if one has two events which occur at different times, like a reflected and incident ray. Furthermore, it ultimately yields Newtonian mechanics, i.e. conservation of momentum for reflection and refraction separately in that one obtains $\theta(i) = \theta(\text{refl})$ and Snell's law.

Thus, there seems to exist a more general theory to Newtonian mechanics which links flux weights with momentum, but also leads to a kind of steady stream book-keeping probability scheme which accounts for momentum conservation, removes time and so allows for events occurring at different times to have their probabilities added together, but then allows for negative probabilities to allow for the reduction in probability of an event at an early time. In this scheme, quantum mechanics is very much a kind of balancing (book-keeping) probability scheme, but it allows for the calculator of both conservation of momentum (classically) and probability weights for reflection and refraction which Newtonian mechanics does not.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that Newtonian mechanics allows one to use conservation of momentum applied separately to reflection and refraction to obtain $\theta(\text{incident}) = \theta(\text{reflected})$ and Snell's law. The problem, we argue, is that Newtonian mechanics does not allow one to calculate the probabilities to reflect and refract, it seems. We suggest that one may introduce a different book-keeping probability scheme which allows one to consider a steady stream picture which involves incident, reflected and refracted photons together and so removes time. The catch is that this book-keeping probability must account for reduction in an incident flux by a reflected one if both appear together. Furthermore, one has average momentum conservation using this new probability. The new probability is not simply a constant weight in space, but should allow one to use any rotated co-ordinate system and so should be invariant under rotations, but should also split into $P(x)P(y)$ factors. This suggests an $\exp(i \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{r})$

solution, where \mathbf{a} is a vector. The only physical vector in question is momentum, so we suggest an $A \exp(i\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{x})$ scheme and balance this probability and its average momentum.

We suggest that this scheme yields both $\theta(i)=\theta(\text{refl})$ and Snell's law, i.e. conservation of momentum in the Newtonian picture, but in the new quantum approach, one requires probability and momentum conservation (using the new probability) to obtain the Newtonian result, but has the added feature of yielding information about reflection and refraction probabilities.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snell%27s_law